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Influence of Underemployment and Perception of Pay Equity on Unethical Work Attitude among the Non-Commissioned Officers in the Nigerian Army

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the influence of underemployment and perceived pay equity on unethical work attitude among non-commissioned officers in the Nigerian army. A cross-sectional survey design which utilizes standardised questionnaire was used to gather the data. Two hundred and twelve (212) Non-commissioned officers (NCO) were purposively sampled from the rank and file personnel at the 81 Division Garrison Obalende, Lagos. 185 (87%) were males and 27 (13%) were females. The mean age is 32.56 (standard deviation = 8.02) years. Three hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. The result revealed that non-commissioned officers high on perceived underemployment significantly recorded higher scores on unethical work attitude than the non-commissioned officers low on underemployment $t(210) = 2.45, p < .05$. Non-commissioned army officers with unfavourable perception of pay equity significantly reported higher scores on unethical work attitude than the non-commissioned officers who have favourable perceptions of pay equity $t(210) = -2.47, p < .01$. The prediction of work attitude by age, marital status, years of experience and education qualification was not significant ($R^2 = .02, F(4,211) = 1.22, p > .05$). However, the independent contribution of age to unethical work attitude was significant ($\beta = .36, p < .05$). The results have practical implications for the recruitment, selection and placement of individuals within the army, given the fact that perception of over qualification and pay equity have a role to play in determining the ethical predispositions of an individual. It was recommended that the military authorities should look into ways of improving the working condition of the non-commissioned army officers.

Key words: Underemployment, Perception of pay equity, Unethical work attitude, non-commissioned army officers

Introduction

In Nigeria, presently, most of the armed security forces record daily occurrence of their personnel's violations of work ethics such as tardiness, gross misconduct and indiscipline in their everyday work life (Odoma, 2014; Oshita, Alumona, & Onuoha, 2019; Sallek, 2018). This is against the value-based attitude of the nature of the job they have been employed to perform. The Nigerian Army historically is an offshoot of the national security design. The military is saddled with the overall responsibility which includes territorial protection against both internal and

external aggression and the protection of life and property of citizens and the Nigerian state (Oshita, et al., 2019; Sallek, 2018). The military's work ethics are built on the ethos which emphasizes duty, loyalty, integrity and courage. Military and paramilitary organisations throughout the world have training models for their officers out of which ethical training or "training on work ethics" is paramount and emphasis is laid on discipline and high exemplary character driven by work ethics (WOLFENDALE, 2009). This value-driven work attitude is seen as the precursor of professionalism (WOLFENDALE, 2009). On the contrary, the core values of the military personnel are said to be gradually declining as the basic essence of being military personnel in Nigeria is being compromised on the basis of self-interest and personal enrichment (Oshita, et al., 2019; Sallek, 2018). In the recent times, military personnel and officers use their position in the military to oppress the innocent members of the public, circumvent the course of justice and use the military machinery to settle ethnic or personal vendettas (Oluyemi, 2020). These poor work ethics were identified to put national security in jeopardy (Oluyemi, 2020; Sallek, 2018).

The level of unethical work practices has reached an alarming level and thus the need to identify factors perpetuating these practices towards providing interventions in stemming this tide (Oshita, et al., 2019). Unethical behaviour among military personnel refers to the making of an official decision in a manner which is contrary to law, arbitrary, unreasonable, without proper justification, lacking in procedural fairness, or made without due consideration of the merits of the matter, or made corruptly. Unethical behaviour can take a variety of forms, ranging from breaking civil or criminal law to disregarding organisational rules.

Nevertheless, numerous factors responsible for this trend have been identified at different fora and have become a subject of research (Adekanye, 2005). However, some salient issues such as underemployment and low utilisation of officers as causal factor in officers' engagement in unethical behaviour have not been examined. Being underutilised may make an individual available for activities that are of no importance to their career. Researchers have described individuals as 'underemployed' when they are working in inferior, lesser, or lower quality jobs relative to some defined standard (Feldman, 1996). This involves individuals' perceptions of whether they feel underemployed or underutilized relative to their expectations of their careers (Feldman & Turnley, 1995; Khan & Morrow, 1991). There are several waiting periods within the military where units or detachments often have little to do regarded as post deployment phase, this may have implications for the performance of the military personnel and job outcome. Between post deployment to pre-deployment phase, service members undergo routine training and medical examinations in order to maintain their personal and unit readiness levels (Buschmann, 2000). This phase is referred to as "normal life," as the service member is at home and works on a regular basis. When not on deployment, military personnel and their units go through standard training to prepare for military tasks or Military Operations Other Than War (MOOTW) (Buschmann, 2000). Some service men were involved in peace keeping, internal security activities or left idle carrying out routine activities at the military barracks and formations. During these periods; service members can expect to get off-duty time to relax with friends, pursue personal interests or hobbies — and discover new ones, too.

Many of the military personnel utilised these free periods to engage in other activities outside their posting. Many of the servicemen utilised different, for many who feel underemployed often use these periods. Many them are usually bored and some may engage in unethical behaviour to beat boredom or make extra cash (Maeland & Brunstad, 2009). This study

thus hypothesized that servicemen who were feel under utilised during post deployment period will likely be involved in unethical practices.

Another variable of importance in this study is perception pay equity. Currently many of the print have identified the declining adequate remuneration and poor working conditions for the Nigerian servicemen (The Guardian, 2021; The Punch, 2020; Abiodun, 2020). Such that many of the servicemen now engage in extra-legal activities in order to supplement and to be able to carryout their operational activities even are in the war theatre zones (The Guardian, 2021; The Punch, 2020). Many researchers assert that unethical work attitude is exhibited by the workers because they feel inequitably treated in the workplace. Literature has showed that most employees naturally compare their ratio of outcomes (i.e. pay raise, and promotions) to inputs (i.e. skill, training, education, and effort) (Henle, 2005). When employees experience similar outcomes in response to similar inputs as compared to other co-workers, employees experience equity. Conversely, when there is a discrepancy between their input versus output ratio and those of others, the employees experience inequity. In order to restore their sense of inequity, employees will often turn to resorting to acts of deviance (Henle, 2005).

The idea is based on equity theory, a theory of motivation (Adams, 1965). Equity theory indicates that a person examines what he brings to a job (inputs) and what he receives from a job (outcomes) and compares that to a reference person, evaluating the other person's inputs and outcomes. If these ratios are not equal, then the employee will feel unfairly treated. If this employee determines that her inputs are far greater than her counterpart's inputs, but their pay is the same, this employee will feel unfairly compensated. Based on this premise, pay inequity have been identified in this study to play significant role in non-commissioned officers' ethical attitude to work. Some officers at the point of recruitment into the military come in with low educational qualification which was upgraded during the course of their stay in the military. However, this does not translate into automatic promotion or elevation in rank for most of these educated junior officers. These lead to officers becoming displeased when they observe officers of the same educational qualification enjoying better pay and privileges. Based on this premise it is suggested that perception of pay inequity will lead to non-commission officers acting unethically in personal encounters.

Empirical studies on the variables identified in the study have shown that underemployment and perception of pay can affect non-commissioned officer job related attitude. The influence of underemployment on employee attitudes was investigated by Nadir, Khan, and Bibi (2017). Underemployment and employee job attitude were shown to have a substantial and unfavourable association in the study. Wage discrimination and its consequences on work-related outcomes were investigated by Falope (2017). The study's findings revealed that employees' perceptions of wage discrimination influenced their work-related results. Employee perceptions of salary discrimination lowered work satisfaction and organisational commitment, but did not contribute to employee turnover intentions, according to the author. This was linked to the study area's lack of work opportunities. Looking at contribution of demographic characteristics to unethical behaviour. Age was found to be a major predictor of ethical behaviour by Peterson, Rhoads, and Vaught (2001). They discovered that elderly individuals have more ethical values and are less affected by those around them at work and at home. Peterson et al. (2001) both found a relationship between gender and age. Their findings show that ethical views evolve at different rates for men and women, with the gaps narrowing as they become older.

Hypotheses tested

H₁: Non-commissioned officers who reported being underemployed will significantly report more unethical work attitude than non-commissioned officers who are well employed.

H₂: Non-commissioned army officers with unfavourable perception of pay equity will significantly report more unethical work attitude than the non-commissioned army officers with favourable perceptions of pay equity.

H₃: The hypothesis which states that age, marital status, years of experience and educational qualification will jointly and independently predict unethical work attitude among the non-commissioned officers.

Methods

Design

The research adopted a cross-sectional design. It used to estimate the incidence of a certain behaviour in a given population. This design was adopted with the aim of having a snap shot of perception of unethical work among non-commission officers and factors associated with it.

Research setting

The setting for the study was the 81 Division Garrison, Nigerian Army Obalende, Lagos State, Nigeria. 81 Division Garrison is an offshoot of the 81 Division which is one of the divisions in the Nigerian Army. The unit provide internal security role within Lagos metropolis and is located at Dodan Barracks, Obalende. The study was restricted to this setting because the unit is one of the combat arms of the army in Lagos State, hence the troops participate in joint patrol within the metropolis. The total population of Military personnel at the time of this study was 763 out of which 212 were selected as the sample size.

Participants

The study population was made up of non-commissioned officers in the Nigerian Army. Two hundred and twelve (212) non-commissioned officers were purposively selected as the study sample from the non-commissioned officers at the 81 Division Garrison Obalende, Lagos. 185 (87%) were males and 27 (13%) were females. The age of the participants ranged from 19 to 54 years. The average age was 32.56 (SD = 8.02) years. Among the officers, 84 (39.62%) were singles, 119(56.13%) were married, 6(2.8%) were divorced and 3(1.4%) widowed. The years of experience ranged from 1 to 35 years with a mean of 12.18 years and standard deviation of 7.2 years. Their educational qualification showed that 97 (45.8%) were SSCE certificate holders, 68 had Ordinary National Diploma (OND) or National Certificate of Education (NCE) certificates, 36 (17%) had first degree qualification, 7 (3.3%) were master's degree holders and 4 (1.9%) had other certificates.

Sampling technique

The study utilised purposive sampling technique was used to select the participants. The participants who were on duty or available at the time of the study and agreed to participate in the study were sampled at their various duty posts within the barracks. Those outside the barracks were reached with the help of the Unit Orderly Corporal who took the researcher to some of these duty locations.

Research instrument

The measure contained a questionnaire pack with demographic data of participants (age, marital status, rank, number of children, educational status, religion etc), Pay Equity Perception Scale (PEPS; Tremblay et al., 2000), Underemployment Scale (US; Feldman & Bolino, 2000) and Unethical Work Attitude Scale (Bryan, 1984). The details are explained thus:

Pay Equity Perception Scale (PEPS)

PEPS consist of five items. The scale assesses respondent perception of distributive justice with regards to their pay and employee benefits, which were broken down into internal equity (immediate supervisor and colleagues) and external equity (other organizations). Participants' response was scored and coded on a 5-point Likert scale ranging from 1- (strongly agree) to (5- strongly disagree on all the items). High scores on each of the item indicate a negative perception of fairness. To have a composite index for perceived pay fairness, the respondent scores on the five items were added together and the score ranged from above 6 – 24. The average score was 15.76 with standard deviation of 4.17. The average score was used to dichotomise the respondent perception scores into favourable and unfavourable perception of pay equity. Respondents with scores below and equal to 15.76 were regarded as having unfavourable perception of pay equity and those with scores above 15.76 were regarded as having favourable perception of pay equity. The authors reported a Cronbach alpha of 0.83. For the present study the scale recorded a reliability index of 0.87 Cronbach alpha.

Perception of underemployment Scale

PUS taps the extent to which non-commissioned officers perceived their assignments as challenging and provide learning opportunities as well as how they fully utilize their education, experience, training, skills, and abilities. Participants used a 5-point scale score and coded: 1- Strongly disagree, 2- Disagree, 3 – Undecided, 4- Agree and 5 - to Strongly Agree to respond to the 13 items. High scores on each of the item indicate perception of underemployment. To have a composite index for perception of underemployment, the respondent scores on the six items were added together and the score ranged from above 6 – 30. The average score was 15.16 with standard deviation of 7.17. The average score was used to dichotomise the respondent perception scores into high and low underemployment. Respondents with scores below and equal to 15.16 were regarded as having low underemployment and those with scores above 15.16 were regarded as having high underemployment perception. The authors reported a Cronbach alpha of 0.83 while the present study recorded a reliability index of 0.76 Cronbach alpha.

Unethical work attitude scale (UWAS)

UWAS consist of 21-items, assess the extent to which non-commissioned officers engaged in unethical professional work attitude. Participants used a 5-point scale score ranging from 1(Strongly disagree) to 5(Strongly Agree) to respond to the 21 items. High scores on each of the item indicate increasing levels of unethical work attitude. Initial reliability carried out to assess the reliability revealed a low index of 0.67. Using 0.3 corrected total item criterion, eleven items which corrected total item index below 0.3 criterion were identified to have weak reliability, were deleted while the items retained where items 1,2, 4, 6, 8, 9, 11, 12, 13, 14 and 15. To have a composite index for unethical professional work attitude, the respondent scores on the ten items were added together and the score ranged from above 6 – 49. Increasing scores suggest increasing

unethical attitude. The authors reported a Cronbach alpha of 0.60 while the present study recorded a reliability index of 0.87 Cronbach alpha.

Procedure

The researchers first sought for permission from the Commander of the unit to carry out the study. After the permission was granted, the purposive sampling technique was used to sample the respondents at their various duty posts. The researcher went about administering questionnaires personally to the non-commissioned officers of the unit at their various duty posts/training shields. Informed consent was obtained from the participants before questionnaires was administered on the participants. Those who decline were not included in the study. The researcher explained to the respondents that the questionnaire contained not personal identifier and strictly for research purpose. They were however assured that the information would be treated confidentially. A total of 250 copies of questionnaire were distributed. The researcher was able to recover 212 copies from the respondents. The questionnaires that were properly completed were used for data analysis.

Data analysis

In analysing the collected data, the researcher utilized descriptive statistics (simple frequency and percentages) to describe the respondent's characteristics. The hypotheses were tested using inferential statistics. Three hypotheses were tested in the study; hypotheses 1 and 2 were tested using t-test for independence measures while hypothesis 3 was tested using multiple regression analysis.

Results

Hypothesis 1: Non-commissioned officers who reported being underemployed will significantly report more unethical work attitude than non-commissioned officers who are well employed. The hypothesis was tested using t-test for independent measures and the summary of the result is presented in Table 1.

Table 1

Results of t-test for independence and descriptive Statistics for unethical work attitude perception of underemployment among commissioned officers

	Underemployment						t	df
	High			Low				
	M	SD	n	M	SD	n		
Unethical work attitude	29.30	7.75	102	31.78	6.68	110	2.45*	210

* $p < .05$.

Table 1, result shows that the non-commissioned officers who scored high on underemployment scale ($\bar{x} = 29.30$, S.D = 7.75) significantly recorded higher scores on unethical work attitude scale than the non-commissioned officers who have low scores on underemployment scale ($\bar{x} = 31.78$, S.D = 6.86). The difference was statistically significant ($t(210) = 2.45$, $p < .05$). This means that non-commissioned officers significantly differ in level of unethical work attitude based on whether they are underemployed or gainfully employed. Thus, hypothesis one which stated that underemployment will significantly influence the non-commissioned officers' unethical attitude to work is supported.

Hypothesis 2: Non-commissioned army officers with unfavourable perception of pay equity will significantly report more unethical work attitude than the non-commissioned army officers with favourable perceptions of pay equity. The hypothesis was tested using t-test for independent measures and the summary of the result is presented below in Table 2:

Table 2
Results of t-test for independence and descriptive Statistics for unethical work attitude perception of perception of pay equity among commissioned officers

	Pay equity						t	df
	Favourable			Unfavourable				
	M	SD	n	M	SD	n		
Unethical work attitude	29.27	7.26	108	31.76	7.41	104	2.47*	210

* $p < .05$.

From Table 2, results show that the non-commissioned army officers with unfavourable perception of pay equity ($\bar{x} = 31.76$, S.D= 7.26) significantly reported higher scores on unethical work attitude than the non-commissioned army officers who have favourable perceptions of pay equity ($\bar{x} = 29.27$, S.D=7.41). The result shows that there is a significant difference in the unethical work attitude reported by the non-commissioned army officers based on their perception of pay equity ($t(210) = 2.47, p < .01$). Hypothesis two which stated that pay equity perception will influence unethical work attitude was accepted.

Hypothesis 3: The hypothesis which states that age, marital status, years of experience and educational qualification will jointly and independently predict unethical work attitude among the non-commissioned officers was tested using multiple regression analysis. The result is presented in Table 3:

Table 3
Summary of multiple regression analysis showing the influence of age, marital status, years of experience and educational qualification on unethical work attitude.

Predictors	β	t-value	Sig.	R	R ²	F	P
				.15	.02	1.22	>.05
Age	.34	1.99	<.05				
Years of experience	-.32	-1.8	>.05				
Marital status	-.05	-.64	>.05				
Education	-.02	-.21	>.05				

The result of the multiple regression analysis revealed that age, marital status, years of experience and education qualification ($r^2 = .02, F(4,211) = 1.22, p > .05$) jointly predicted 2% of the variance observed in the reported unethical work attitude scores of the non-commissioned officers and this was not significant. The result also revealed the independent influence of age ($\beta = .36, p < .01$) on unethical work attitude among the non-commissioned officers sampled in the study. The direction of the relationship shows that the non-commissioned officers who are young reported higher unethical work attitude than those that were older. Years of experience ($\beta = -.32, p > .05$), marital

status ($\beta = -.32, p > .05$) and educational qualification ($\beta = .07, p > .05$) did not independently predict unethical work attitude among the non-commissioned officer. The hypothesis stated that socio-demographic variable will predict unethical work behaviour is partially supported.

Discussion

This study examined the psychological factors promoting unethical work attitude among the Non-commissioned officers from the 81 Division Garrison in Obalende barracks, Lagos, Nigeria. The first hypothesis which stated that Non-commissioned military officers will differ in unethical work attitude based on their perception of whether they are underemployed or being gainfully employed was supported. Underemployed non-commissioned officers reported higher levels of unethical attitude. This supports the local saying that the idle hand is the devil's workshop. Holding a job that is below one's educational credentials is a form of underemployment (Maynard et al., 2006). Underemployment can also be a source of job dissatisfaction, which in turn, may lead to higher turnover intentions and other work withdrawal symptoms (Johnson & Johnson, 2002b). Fine and Nevo (2008) found a negative relationship between underemployment and job satisfaction for customer service representatives. This finding also supports the finding of Feldman and Bolino (2000) that demonstrated that employee's underemployment is negatively related to expatriates' job attitudes, general mental health, and self-reported job performance.

Hypothesis two which stated that non-commissioned army officers with unfavourable perception of pay equity will significantly report more unethical work attitude than the non-commissioned army officers with favourable perception of pay equity was confirmed. The result shows that there is a significant difference in the unethical work attitude reported by the non-commissioned army officers based on their perception of pay equity. People do not want to be undervalued, and low pay may also indicate lower status and lower job importance (Landy & Conte, 2004). When an employee perceives that he is treated fairly, it is logical that he consequently feels satisfied and committed to the job. The perception of being unfairly treated leads to poor job attitude and dysfunctional behaviours. A perceived mismatch between compensation and the worth of one's contributions could lead to poor job attitude. This finding supports the work of Stecher and Rosse (2005) who demonstrated that both distributive justice and interactional justice produced main effects on negative emotion, intention to leave an organisation and reduced work effort. This finding also supports the findings of Sigtler and Adams (1999) who found that pay rate differentiated those who stayed at the job and those who voluntarily left.

Hypothesis three stated that age, marital status, years of experience and education qualification will jointly and independently predict unethical work attitude among the non-commissioned officers was partially supported. The result of the multiple regression analysis revealed that age, marital status, years of experience and educational qualifications joint prediction of unethical work attitude of the non-commissioned officers was not significant. Age was the only significant predictor of unethical work attitude as non-commissioned officers who are young reported higher unethical work attitude than those that were older. The influence of marital status, years of experience and educational qualification were not significant. This result gives credence to other studies (Wellmaker, 1985) that have found similar results that education has no significant influence on policemen's work attitude. This finding is consistent with the findings of Adebayo (2005) who demonstrated that age predicted police ethical behaviour. One plausible explanation for differences in ethical beliefs between old and young Non-commissioned army officers' concerns changes in societal values and expectations. This finding may have

occurred as a result that increasing age influences. The Socioemotional selectivity theory (Carstensen, 1992) provides a converging evidence that age moderates employees' job-related attitude as they grow older. Thus as the non-commissioned who were older age were shown to prioritize down-regulate negative youthful exuberance and were less prone to unethical due to being more mature and psychological stable.

Conclusion and recommendation

This study examined the psycho-social factors influencing the unethical work behaviour among Non-commissioned military officers in southwest Nigeria. This study thus concluded that the perception of being underemployed influenced the non-commissioned officer unethical attitude. The study also demonstrated that those who perceived pay inequity reported high scores on unethical behaviour scale. In addition, age and marital status were found to predict unethical behaviour among the officers. Younger unmarried non-commissioned officers recorded higher unethical work attitude compared to the older and married non-commissioned officers. Poorly utilised and remunerated non-commissioned military officers may become a security threat if proper attention and intervention are not put in place to address work related problems among the non-commissioned officers. The results of this study have practical implications for the recruitment, selection and placement of individuals within the army, given the fact that perception of over-qualification, pay, age and marital status have a role to play in determining the ethical predispositions of an individual (Afolabi & Adesina, 2006).

Based on the findings concluded from the analysis and discussion of the results, this study recommends the following:

1. Military authorities should look into ways of improving the working condition of the non-commissioned army officers especially in the area of personnel career development.
2. Also, those NCOs who have acquired higher qualification should be granted presidential commission into the officer cadre.
3. The military as a body should improve the ethical behaviour of its officers by improving on the certified code of ethics. That is, strict and adequate punishment should follow non-compliance to the code of ethics.
4. This study recommends that ethics and ethical training should be offered in the course of training of the non-commissioned army officers.

Limitation of study and future recommendations for further studies

One of the limitations of this study is that it is cross-sectional in strategy thus causal effect relationship could not be established in this study. Secondly, the study is limited to a unit in the military formation in the Nigerian Army, thus the generalisation of the research findings to the whole Nigerian Army may be limited due to its level of its sophistication and differences in policy as regards different units and formations. The study focused on perception of pay and educational qualification. In the future, it is suggested that the key constructs which include underemployment and pay equity be further explored and compared across other occupational groups within the Nigerian military.

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